

Naturalista sicil., S. IV, XLVII (1), 2023, pp. 129-131

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8164892>

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EU PESTICIDE REGULATION CONCERNING
INSECT POLLINATORS: PAST, PRESENT AND FUTURE

La normativa europea su pesticidi e impollinatori: passato, presente e futuro

APITOX, a group of independent scientists with interest on bee toxicology, is a task force of COLOSS (<https://coloss.org>), the association studying causes of honey bee losses globally. Apitox is focused on the ecotoxicological causes of bee mortality, and thus studies the effects and routes of exposure of pesticides on bees, designs methodology for the assessment of these effects, promotes risks assessment protocols effective in protecting bees. The authors of the present paper are both coordinators of APITOX.

The one-way relationship between pesticides and bees is structured in two phases: exposure and effects. The former follows the phytosanitary treatment and the latter is what happens with the bee, once got in contact with the toxic substance.

It is known that during a treatment with insecticides and fungicides, only a very small part of the pesticide reaches the pest or pathogen, while the rest is there in the environment, ready to produce damage to non-target organisms, like beneficial insects, among which pollinators. Since the beginning of risk assessment on bees, honey bee has been considered the model insect for the entire category of pollinators. Nevertheless, there is no reason to hope that the other bee species or unmanaged honey bees are excluded from this destiny. For this reason the scientific community is recently working on the elaboration of the methods to test pesticide effects on non-*Apis* bees.

Said this, there is a need to legally protect bees against agrochemicals. This is done through laws which regulate the authorisation of pesticides, which includes a pre-authorisation assessment of their effects on bees and other non-target organisms.

Till 1993 each country decided its own procedure and protection criteria for the authorisation of pesticides on the local market. This involved that each country performed the risk assessment of pesticides in its own way.

Subsequently a European authorisation system was promoted, first as an EC directive (91/414/EEC), and since 2011 as a regulation (Reg. EU 1107/2009), with strong legal consequences and a full harmonisation across EU countries.

Moreover the Uniform Principle legislation (Reg EU 546/2011), entered into life in 2011, defines harmonised thresholds for risk assessment and decision making. This legislation defines the trigger values of risk coefficients, the ones that define if higher tier studies need to be done or not.

The regulation EU 1107/2009 is based on the precautionary principle, which means that a pesticide can be authorised only if it is proved that all the authorisation conditions are respected. For the same principle a pesticide can be banned if new data show risk which was initially ignored.

Summarising, a pesticide can be authorised only if it:

- shows no unacceptable effects on plants or plant products,
- causes no suffering to vertebrates,
- has no immediate or delayed, direct or indirect harmful effects on human and animal health, including cumulative and synergistic effects,
- shows no unacceptable influence on the environment (fate, non-target organisms, biodiversity and ecosystems).

The regulation EU 1107/2009 provides also the definition of “unacceptable” and determines Specific Protection Goals (SPG), i.e. what (colonies, populations, ...) needs to be protected and when (at pesticide application, afterwards, ...), where (everywhere, in the field, field edge, ...) and why (for pollination, food production, cultural heritage, biodiversity, genetic diversity, etc.)

Regarding different bee species, since non-target organisms are mentioned in the regulation, there is a legal framework for the protection of pollinators different than honey bees. In practice honey bees have their own legal mention historically, thus also in the Regulation EU 1107/2009 they are protected in a separate way from the other arthropods. In other words, general protection goals are already defined by the Member States. Now the game is to translate general protection goals into something workable in practice.

Actually, Member States already set SPGs for honey bees and are now setting SPGs for other bees.

It is interesting to notice that the regulation mentions separately honey bees, which means that the distinction is made on the taxonomic basis (and not on the basis of usefulness).

As a result, managed and unmanaged honey bee colonies are in theory protected by law in the same way.

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